
CUSTOMERS–BANKERS RELATIONSHIP AND BANK PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA: AN APPRAISAL OF BANK SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the customers/banker's relationship and bank performance in Nigeria: An appraisal of Bank services. The specific objectives are Customer demand, Information technology, banker/customer, bank services and bank performance. Primary data were sourced through the use of a structured questionnaire while one hundred and twenty questionnaires were administered to customers of which eighty were returned and used for this research. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The descriptive involved frequency and percentage while inferential are regression and Correlation analysis. The results revealed that banker/customer and bank performance ($r[80] = 0.975, p < 0.01$); customer demand ($p < 0.05$) and banker/customer and information technology ($r[80] = 0.818, p < 0.01$). The study concluded that formal training of bankers on how to treat customers improves customer satisfaction and likewise, the effective policy on banker/customer relationship facilitates banks efficiency, there is high satisfaction of customer demand of bank services which means that there are effective and efficient services that enhance customers' satisfaction and with the way they treat their customers and the introduction of information technology has been of a benefit to customers and the banks which has a greater impact in attracting the customers to the bank.

Keywords: *Customers' demands, information technology, bank services, bank performance.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer relationship management is defined as the overall process of building and maintaining profitable customer relationships by delivering superior customer value and satisfaction. (Kotler and Armstrong 2010). Also, it could be defined as managing detailed information about individual customers and carefully managing customer “touchpoints” to maximize customer loyalty (Kotler, John and James, 2010). According to Eta (2016), providing high-quality service to consumers is without a doubt one of the most essential issues in the banking business. All banks have continuously and repeatedly proclaimed their efficiency in providing high-quality personal service to their consumers in their advertising messaging. The bank is aware of the need for customer service and is making an effort to meet those demands.

Customer relationship management has piqued the interest of many practitioners and academics. For effective and efficient customer relationships, an increasing number of businesses are adopting customer-centric strategies, programs, tools, and technology. They recognize the importance of in-depth customer understanding to develop close mutual and collaborating ties with their consumers. The emergence of new channels and technology is dramatically altering how businesses interact with their customers, resulting in a greater degree of integration between marketing, sales, and customer support responsibilities in educational institutions. In the Nigerian banking industry, Customer Service Management (CSM) has grown increasingly significant. According to Ezeoha (2007), the banking industry is today facing fundamental business issues, including survival and success in a volatile market.

To ensure improved performance, Nigerian banks must adopt down to business ways as they face more changes, increased competition, and continually growing client needs and prospects.

As a result, establishing and maintaining a good business reputation has become increasingly difficult (Khong, 2005); the result of internal division, which customers notice and comment on, is now visible globally in the era of the social customer. To address fragmentation, an organization's philosophy and culture must change so that everyone analyses the influence of policy, decisions, and actions on customers (Hart-Davidson, Bernhardt, McLeod, Rife, and Grabill, 2008; Kostelnick, 1998). Human interaction at all levels of the organization can have a positive or negative impact on the customer experience; even one disgruntled customer can deliver a body blow to a company (Pennington, 2007). The purpose of this study is to look into and analyse the strategic performance of Customer Relationship Management and its impact on the performance of Nigerian banks. The hypothesis is an assumption about a population that may be examined or verified to satisfy the research's goal and objective. The study's goal is to see if the following hypothesis is true.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no effective relationship between bankers/customers and banks' performance;

H₀₂: There is low satisfaction of customer demands on banks services;

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between technology and banker/customer relationship.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework of Banking

In a financial institution, the importance of the banker-customer connection cannot be overstated in terms of the services provided by the banker to the consumers. The importance of bank-customer connection has prompted modern banking to focus on or investigate more financial packages capable of retaining existing customers while also attracting new ones. According to Patrick I. Osiebgu, the connection between bankers and customers is more akin to that between debtors and creditors. Only when the customer opens an account with the bank is the relationship stated to begin. Relationship banking is a tactic employed by banks to increase their profit margins. They accomplish this through cross-selling financial products and services to customers to strengthen their relationships and increase customer loyalty.

Relationship banking entails providing a wide range of financial products and services to customers that extend beyond simple checking and savings accounts. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has evolved as a strategy for sustaining positive customer connections, boosting client loyalty, and enhancing customer lifetime value (Brassington & Pettit, 2000).

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is described as a company's procedures for systematically managing customers to optimize value throughout the relationship lifecycle (Martin, Oliver, and Jacquelyn, 2010). Customer relationship management is also defined as the practice of establishing and maintaining profitable customer relationships by providing superior customer value and satisfaction. (Kotler and Armstrong 2010, for example) Furthermore, it could be regarded as carefully managing customer "touchpoints" and managing precise information about individual consumers to maximize customer loyalty (Kotler and Armstrong 2010). As the company seeks to improve its return through long-term connections with customers, anticipating customer needs and offering value-added relationship management is becoming increasingly important. Many years ago, financiers introduced the concept of value maximization, in which a company optimizes profits while maximizing utility. We now have the notion of Customer Relationship Management (CRM). Many companies have previously invested extensively in Information Technology (IT) assets to better manage their interactions with customers before, during, and after purchase (Bohling, Lavallo, Mittal, Narayandas, Ramani, and Varadarajan, 2006). As a result, the more we learn about how companies successfully build and combine their technological and organizational capabilities, the more we'll understand how Customer Relationship Management affects performance (Swift, 2000), Bharadwaj, 2000; Piccoli & Ives, 2005). Shain and Taylor (1992) defined relationship marketing as an integrated effort to identify, maintain, and strengthen a network with individual customers. (Kubat and Harrison, 2003; Giudici & Passerone, 2002). Furthermore, the high competition encourages them to switch items quickly if they are dissatisfied. As a result, consumer retention is essential. To keep customers, effective customer service is required. as a result of this, an effective CSM (Khong and Richardson, 2003).

Theoretical Framework of Banker Customer Relationship

Relationship banking, as typified by retail banks, is a valuable enabling approach that increases competitiveness and delivers long-term success, according to Ravestyn, (2003) "the effect and relationship of banking in customer loyalty on the retail business banking environment." Relationship banking as a banking strategy to boost client retention, create customer loyalty, and eventually increase long-term returns is a relatively new concept, first introduced in the 1980s and gaining traction in the 1990s. The proper submission of relationship banking could have a positive impact on banks' baseline.

As a result, the purpose of this study is to look into the impact of relationship banking on customer loyalty, as well as its use in determining customer loyalty and long-term value from relationship banking schemes. Banks must understand their customers' behaviour and trading habits to promote relationship strategies. Market fragmentation is a critical part of relationship marketing, and corporate customer segmentation must reflect the various degrees of relationship contributions. Because of this fragmentation, banks will be able to provide the appropriate relationship banking help to the appropriate customer.

Banks must be able to determine individual client returns to assist in the segmentation process. After segmentation, banks must implement and employ appropriate "CRM" (customer relationship management) strategies and CRM systems to support the relationship banking offering.

Customers across all industrial sectors are becoming more aware of the level of choice and competition for their business, according to Morgan Sarshar and Paul Parry. This has taken precedence over firms' obligations to expand and maintain marketing strategies that will boost their competitiveness within their industry. Relationship marketing (RM) is a marketing theory that has benefited businesses in a variety of industries, while its perspective in the service (FM)

sector may be relatively recent. The goal of this article is to see if the Nigerian financial market sector is aware of the RM theory and is putting it into practice today.

Empirical Framework of Banker Customer Relationship

According to Nnolin (1995), who wrote an article for the journal "the management in Nigeria," commercial bank goods that the Nigerian consumer desires are:

- i. Credit facilities
- ii. Payment facilities

He went on to clarify that the order in which he desires them is not determined by his impression of the services or products' availability to him. Furthermore, it was said that the Nigerian commercial bank customer has become rather sophisticated in his need for non-basic services, yet the number has not expanded as quickly as one might think. Customer satisfaction is recognized as a key aspect of every bank's business strategy. It's a location on the worktable where a company must set its goal. When a company's goods or services match the expectations and needs of its clients, it thrives.

A strong customer service administration effort can also help Nigerian banks manage their client relationships more effectively, resulting in increased productivity. Given the foregoing, it is clear that successful CSM activities should result in improved business results. Market orientation, according to Piercy and Cravens (2003), is a philosophy that governs the process of delivering customer value. Superior performance will result from superior customer value. According to Kumar and Reinartz (2006), customer happiness is a vital mediator that leads to increased retention or loyalty, which leads to increased profit for a company.

These linkages are not always well-built, however, because they are affected by environmental factors such as the ferocity of competition, the degree of switching cost, and the level of perceived risk in various industries (Kumar & Reinartz, 2006).

Customer satisfaction is a conceivable task in a business, according to Hoffman and Bateson (2006). It covers a wide range of activities, including product and service quality, fair pricing, human resource development, and on-time delivery. Enriching these aspects can help close the gap between consumer expectations and perceptions; these gaps emerge when what customers anticipate receiving falls short of their expectations. As a result, delighting customers entails closing the customer gap to meet or surpass customer expectations, according to Kolter and Keller (2006).

Quality, innovation, and distinctiveness of products and services are always inspired by transforming and improving their features, approaches, and distinctiveness. Transforming and improving product and service features aims to increase customer sensitivity and create competitive advantages due to their exceptionality. Furthermore, new features can help to establish "the Company's image as an innovator" and win the allegiance of market segments who value these characteristics (Kolter & Keller, 2006).

Customer happiness is the best strategy to maintain customers' future purchases if a firm wants to keep them (Taylor & Baker, 1994; Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Parasuraman et. al, 1988). Individual needs, wishes, and expectations concerning the value of the product or service can be measured by some of the following elements, according to Jamal and Naser (2003): "service quality has been described as a form of attitude that results from the comparison of expectations with performance." Individual needs, wishes, and expectations concerning the value of the product or service can be measured by some of the following elements, such as friendly and

helpful salespersons, informed advice, reasonable price, high quality, and a long guarantee period (Adjamiet al, 2008).

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research approach is a rational way to come up with a solution to a specific problem. This chapter explains the methodology used to conduct the research. The sample and sampling technique, data gathering, and data analysis are the study mechanisms used. The research design is a blueprint that outlines how data or information about a study problem should be acquired and processed while keeping time and resources in mind (Annyiwe, Idahosa, & Ibeh, 2005).

This study employed a survey research design rather than an experimental research design. The situation was researched and analysed thoroughly. Nonetheless, data collected from surveys were reviewed and evaluated as part of the study. The surveys were given to 120 people, however, only 80 of them answered all of the questions completely.

Population and Sample Size

The overall population of this study for detailed evaluation was commercial banks in the Shagamu metropolitan area; the scope of this study was confined to the following banks.

- i. First Bank of Nigeria PLC
- ii. Zenith Bank of Nigeria PLC
- iii. Wema Bank of Nigeria PLC
- iv. Guarantee Trust Bank Limited
- v. United Bank for Africa

Sampling Techniques

A sample is that part of the population on which further analysis is sought, while the act of sampling as opined by Chinelo (1996) “is the process of selecting a subset of observations from among many possible observations, to conclude the larger set of possible observations”. The purpose of this sampling technique is that is a method that permits the researcher to objectively select the sample units from the researcher population based on his understanding of the population.

To avoid unbiased data collection, a simple random sampling technique was used, in other to sample out the five commercial banks in Nigeria.

Methods of Data Collection

It is unmistakably clear that in other to achieve the objectives of the study and to have an extensive understanding of it, data must be sourced. The data collected for this research comprises Primary data which are information sourced from respondents although the administration of questionnaires, interviews or by participation and observation for better illumination.

Techniques of Data Analysis

The data was evaluated employing Analysis of Variance ANOVA, this is adopted to assess the significance of distinct options for both the customers and the bankers. The ANOVA statistics will make use of F- statistics. Regression correlation analysis is also to be used because the R-value of the relationship between two variables will be Measured Also regression analysis is also adopted to analyse the hypothesis.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Gender distribution of respondents revealed that thirty-six (45%) of the respondents are female while forty-four (55%) are male. Age distribution of the respondents showed that fourteen (17.5%) are between 18-27 years out of eighty respondents, twelve (15%) of the respondents are between 28-37 years, and nineteen (23.8%) are between 38-47 years while thirty-five (43.8%) of the respondents are 48 years and above. The marital status of the respondents revealed that twenty-five (31.2%) are married while fifty-five (68.8%) are Single. Educational qualifications revealed that twenty-four (30%) are NCE/ND holders, fifty (62.5%) are HND/B.Sc. while six (7.5%) are MBA/M.Sc. holders.

Occupation of respondents revealed that forty-eight (60%) are civil servants while thirty-two (40%) are private workers. It was also revealed that twenty-nine (36.3%) of the respondents are the customers banking with First Bank Nigeria Plc., thirteen (16.3%) are the customers banking with Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, ten (12.5%) are the customers banking with Eco Bank Nigeria Plc and twenty-eight (35%) are the customers banking with Keystone bank Limited. The years of banking with the bank showed that thirty-one (38.8%) have been dealing with the bank between 1-10 years, twenty-five (31.3%) have been banking with the bank between 11-20 years while twenty-four have been banking with the bank between 21-30 years.

Table 4.1: Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percent
<u>Gender Distribution</u>		
Female	36	45.0
Male	44	55.0
Total	80	100
<u>Age Distribution</u>		
18-27 Years	14	17.5
28-37 Years	12	15.0
38-47 Years	19	23.8
48 Years and above	35	43.8
Total	80	100.0
<u>Marital Status</u>		
Married	25	31.2
Single	55	68.8
Total	80	100.0
<u>Educational Qualification</u>		
NCE/ND	24	30.0
HND/B.Sc.	50	62.5
MBA/M.Sc.	6	7.5
Total	80	100.0
<u>Occupation</u>		
Civil Servant	48	60.0
Private	32	40.0
Total	80	100.0
<u>Bank</u>		
First Bank of Nigerian Plc.	29	36.3
Union Bank of Nigerian Plc.	13	16.3
Eco Bank Nigeria Plc.	10	12.5
Keystone Bank Limited	28	35.0
Total	80	100.0
<u>Years</u>		
1-10 years	31	38.8
11-20 years	25	31.3
21- 30 years	24	30.0
Total	80	100.0

Source: Author's Computation (2021)

Hypothesis One

There is no effective relationship between Banker/customer and banks performance

The correlation of two variables, banker/customer and bank performance was analyzed. Data were obtained from 80 respondents using Pearson Product moment correlation.

The result as presented in Table 4.2 shows that there is a significant positive relationship between banker/customer and bank performance ($r [80] = 0.975$, $p < 0.01$). Obtaining a probability of 0.000 which is less than the 0.01 significance level for a two-tailed test, the banker/customer and bank performance is significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, that there is no significant relationship between banker/customer and bank performance. This suggests that formal training of bankers on how to treat customers improves customer satisfaction and likewise the effective policy on banker/customer relationship facilitates banks' efficiency.

Table 4.2: Correlation Co-efficient between banker/customer and Bank performance

Correlations			
		Banker/customer	Bank Performance
Banker/customer	Pearson Correlation	1	0.975**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	80	80
Bank Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.975**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	80	80

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Computation (2021)

Hypothesis Two

There is no low satisfaction of customer demands on bank services

To test this hypothesis, the respondents' scores on two variables customer demand for bank services were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. From Table 4.3, the R (correlation Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.747; this indicates that there is a very strong and positive relationship between customer demands for bank services. The R^2 is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R^2 is equal to 0.558, this implies that customer demand for bank services brought about 55.8% variance in bank services, this is further proven by the adjusted R^2 that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.553, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made the model can only account for 55.3% by customer demand while the remaining 44.7% are explained by the error term in the model.

The unstandardized beta co-efficient of customer demand is 0.563 with $t = 9.931$ and ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$). These results showed that customer demand affects bank services. It is found significant; therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that is high satisfaction of customer demand for bank services which means that there are effective and efficient services that enhance customers' satisfaction and the way they treat their customers. The findings are in line with Hoffman and Bateson (2006) who said customer satisfaction is a possible task in an organization.

Table 4.3: Estimated effect of Customer demand and bank services

Dependent variable	Bank Services			
	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	2.030	0.202	10.070	0.000
Customer Demand	0.563	0.057	9.931	0.000
R	0.747			
R Square	0.558			
Adj. R Square	0.553			
F- Stat.	(98.631)	0.000		

Source: Author's Computation (2021)

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between technology and banker/customer relationship

The correlation of two variables, banker/customer and information technology were analyzed. Data were obtained from 80 respondents using Pearson Product moment correlation. The result as presented in Table 4.4 shows that there is a significant positive relationship between banker/customer and information technology ($r [80] = 0.818, p < 0.01$). Obtaining a probability of 0.000 which is less than the 0.01 significance level for a two-tailed test, the banker/customer and information technology is significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, that there is a significant relationship between banker/customer and information technology. This implies that the introduction of information technology has been of benefit to customers and the banks which has a greater impact on attracting the customers to the bank. The findings correlate with the work of Piercy and Cravens (2003) who derived market orientation as a philosophy contriving the process for delivering customer value. Also, Eta (2016) found out there is a positive link between the adoption of cutting edge technology by the firm and the banker/customer relationship. This is in agreement with Kolter and Keller (2006) who confirmed that the quality and innovation of products and services are always inspired by transforming and improving their features, approaches and distinctiveness transform the features of products and services aim to raise customer sensitivity and create competitive advantages due to their exceptionality.

Table 4.4: Correlation Co-efficient between banker/customer and technology

Correlations			
		Banker/customer	Technology
Banker/customer	Pearson Correlation	1	0.818**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	80	80
Technology	Pearson Correlation	0.818**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	80	80

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Computation (2021)

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, it is concluded that formal training of bankers on how to treat customers improves customer satisfaction and likewise, the effective policy on banker/customer relationship facilitates banks efficiency, there is high satisfaction of customer demand of bank services which means that there are effective and efficient services that enhance customers'

satisfaction and with the way they treat their customers and the introduction of information technology has been of a benefit to customers and the banks which has a greater impact in attracting the customers to the bank.

Recommendations

The study recommends the following to the banks in Nigeria and other parastatals that will need the results to work with.

- i. Banks should ensure that well trained and experienced professionals should be in charge of customer service to have good results.
- ii. The adoption of customer relationship marketing requires the involvement of everyone in the bank from the customer service department up to the top management staff should be part of those involved in establishing cordial relationships with customers.
- iii. It could be related to more marketing of the product by the staff as well as the bank itself on a wider scale.

REFERENCES

- Annyiwe, M.A Idahosa D.O and Ibeh S.E (2005) Basic Research Method in Social Science Mindex, Press Benin City.
- Bharadwaj, A.S. (2000). "A Resource-based Perspective on Information Technology, Gradability and Firm Performance: An Empirical Investigation". *Mis Quarterly* 24(1), 169-196 Doi: 100-1007/s11747- 009-0164-y.
- Bohling, T.B., Lavalle, S., Mittal, V. Narayandas, D., Ramani, G. and Varadarajan, R. (2006). CRM Implementation; Effectiveness Issues and Insights, *Journal of Services Research* 9(2), 184-194. tcoltman@uow.edu.au.
- Brassington, E., & Pettit, S. (2000) *Principles of Marketing* (Tenth Edition), London: Prentice-Hall.
- Chinelo, G. O., & Guy, C. I. (1996). *Fundamentals of Research Methods*. Enugu: *Optimal Publishers*.
- Cronin, J.J Jr, and Taylor (1992) "Measuring Service Quality: A Re-Examination and Extension" *Journal of Marketing* 56: 55-68
- Eta, A. E. (2016). The Effectiveness of Bankers/Customer Relationship in Banks Performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 8(31), 11-20.
- Ezeoha, A. (2007) 'Structural effects of banking industry consolidation in Nigeria: a review', *Journal of Banking Regulation*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 159–178.
- Giudici, P. and Passerone, G. (2002), "Data Mining of Association Structures to Model Consumer Behaviour. 'Computational Statistics and Data Analysis", 38,533-541.
- Hart-Davidson, W., Bernhardt, G., McLeod, M., Rife, M. and Grabill, G. T. (2008), "Coming to Content Management: Inventing Infrastructure for Organizational Knowledge Work," *Technical Communication Quarterly* 17(1), 10-34.
- Hoffman, K.& Bateson, J. (2006). *Services marketing: Concepts, strategies and cases*. 3rdEdn., Mason, OH: Thomson /South-Western.
- Jamal and Naser (2003) "Factors Influencing Customers Satisfaction in the Retail Banking Sector in Pakistan. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 13 (2): 29-53.

- Khong, K. W. (2005), "The Perceived Impact of Successful Outsourcing on Customer Service Management", *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 10(5), 402-411.
- Khong, K. W. and Richardson, S. (2003), "Business Process Re-engineering (BPR) in Malaysian Banks and Finance Companies", *Managing Service Quality*, 13(1), 54-71.
- Kostelnick, C. (1998), "Conflicting Standards for Designing Data Displays: Following, Flouting, and Reconciling Them." *Technical Communication*, 45(4), 473- 85.
- Kotler, P and K.L Keller (2006) *Marketing Management* New Jersey, Pearson- Prentice Hall
- Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (2010) *Principles of Marketing* 13th edition Pearson Education, Inc. Upper Saddle River New Jersey USA. ISBN-13:978-0-13- 700669-4/10987654321.
- Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (2010) *Principles of Marketing* 13th edition Pearson Education, Inc. Upper Saddle River New Jersey USA. ISBN-13:978-0-13- 700669-4/10987654321.
- Kotler, P. John T. Bowen and James C. Makens (2010) *Marketing for Hospitality and Tourism*. 5th edition, Pearson Education, Inc. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, USA. ISBN-13: 978-0-13-245313-4.
- Kubat, M. and Harrison T. (2003). "Item Set Trees for Targeted Association Querying" *IEE Transaction on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 15, Pp. 1522- 1534.
- Kumar, V. and W.J Reinartz (2006). *Customer Relationship Management A Database Approach* USA, John Wiley and Son, Inc.
- Martin, R. Oliver, S. and Jacquelyn S.T. (2010). "Customer Relationship Management and Firm Performance the Mediating Role of Business Strategy", *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 38, 326-346. Doi 10.1007/s11747-009- 0164-y.
- Nnolin D.A (1995) *Marketing of Commercial Bank Services, Management in Nigeria*. The Macmillan Press Ltd Page 8
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A.& Berry, L. L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing and Marketing Studies*, 64(1):12-40.
- Pennington, L. (2007), "Surviving the Design and Implementation of a Content Management System." *Journal of Business & Technical Communication*, 21(1), 62- 73.
- Piccoli G., and Ives, B. (2005), IT- Dependent Strategic Initiatives and Sustained Competitive Advantage: A Review and Synthesis of the Literature; *MIS quarterly* 29 Pp 747-777
- Piercy, N. F., Cravens, D. W., & Lane, N. (2003). Sales manager behaviour control strategy and its consequences: The impact of manager gender differences. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 23(3), 221-237.
- Shain, R. Merrick and Taylor (1992), *Marketing Payback*, Harlow: Pearson.
- Swift, P. (2000), Predictors and Actors of Openness to Change in a Re-organizing workplace. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85, 132-142.
- Taylor, S.A and T.L Baker (1994) "An Assessment of the Relationship Between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in the Formation of Consumers' Purchase Intentions" *Journal of Retailing* 70 (2): 163.178.